

A Critical Appraisal of Selected Criminological Theories and Their Application to Crime in Contemporary Nigeria

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Abstract

This study critically examines some selected criminological theories and their application to the causes of crime in contemporary Nigeria. Biogenic theory- argues that criminal behaviour is genetically determined. Psychological theory- maintains that factors that encourage crime commission can be located within the criminal. Strain theory posits that stress, or strain caused as a result of blocking opportunity can lead to frustration and criminalities. The means-end theory emphasizes that the legal means of achieving set goals in society are not always overtly available to all members equally at a sane time hence, people tend to be innovative illegally in reaching societal set goals. Differential Opportunity theory reasoned that people in different areas do not have equal access to participation in criminalities. Differential Association theory stresses that criminal behaviour is learned in much the same way as normal behaviour and that for one to become a criminal depends largely on whom one interacts with within a social milieu. The study aptly demonstrated how each of the theories can be used to explain why people engage in committing crimes in contemporary Nigeria. The study concludes that theory and fact are the firm pillars of academic criminology.

Keywords: Biogenic, Strain, Means-Ends, Differential Opportunity, Differential Association.

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Senator Akaenye (2025).

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Introduction

Studies in Criminology are built and embedded on two great pillars; facts and theories. We must understand what the facts are, and also theories must be advanced to explain those facts. But, in the real world, neither facts nor theories revealed themselves to us in prefabricated ways. Theories are propounded to nets cast to catch the cosmic world: to rationalize, to explain, and to master the world, and to help make it ever finer and finer. Theories help us to answer questions they also explain the relationships between events and provide causal explanations among variables. Theories confirm and relate to us why or how it is, the facts objectively observed are as they appear.

Adler, Mueller, and Laufer (1991), aptly explain theory to mean a systematic set of principles that help to explain how two or more phenomena are causally related. Theory denotes a body of ideas, which has been accepted as capable of explaining a causal relation between two or more phenomena.

The theory of crime vividly represents an organized, systematic and formalized body of reason\idea which is generally accepted and capable of giving plausible explanations on the causal relationships between some variables on the phenomenon of crime aetiology. Theorist engagement in critical

theorizing about a given or relational phenomenon is a sought-after mental exercise in academics, and it also requires all the processes and methodology of the physical sciences: observation, classification, and measurement. As a prerequisite, theory should, or must contain hard facts which have been tested, showing the relationships existing between and among some variables in the cosmic world. Therefore, the study has it as its major objective to explore some selected criminological theories to explain those causative factors that animate people to crime commission in contemporary Nigerian society.

Literature Review on the Origin and Nature of Criminological Theories

Views are divided among scholars and criminologists as to what animates individuals to engage in criminal activities in human society. The quest for what causes crime has preoccupied first, classical philosophers and later researchers in behavioural and social sciences including sociologists and criminologists. Interest in crime indeed has led to an abundance of theories, initially, in the field of sociology, and later in criminology, to account for its causes. The various theories, in their combinations or individual patterns, simply show the various

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researchers' views on the phenomenon of crime in the social world (see also Riley, 1963:7; Dubin, 1969).

Pyle et al. (1974) argued that different theories can unearth criminal behaviour within the broad field of criminology alone and that it has become a universally accepted thing to view such abhorrent behaviour as multi-dimensional. These writers warn that certain considerations such as time and available resources can limit or stop a comprehensive interrogation as may be desired. Therefore, all curious researchers engaging in similar investigations must just continue to make their contributions to the ever-expanding body of literature by organizing their efforts on manageable studies that can aid, in providing a part to the whole body of criminal causality enterprise (1974: 9). It was argued that no one unit form of crime is best accounted for by a single theoretical strand or any specific model or paradigm. A different combination of theories seems to be the best to support a sociological and criminological analysis of criminal behaviour (Johnstone, 1983, Johnson, 1979; Linde, 1978; Brown et al., 1991). Faulting a mono-causal explanation of crime, Abrahamsen (1944:4) avers that one factor (for example biological deficiency, unfavourable social conditions or a poor ecology) cannot offer a holistic explanation of criminal behaviour. Unfavourable social circumstances can in one way, as he claims,

have causative significance if they are tied with a given tendency or disposition- This combines a sociological analysis with a psychological one, and Thurston (1942: 51), also argued that there is "no single unit cause of crime" and that each case study unearths "many causative factors". Svancar comes to related conclusions as was cited and interpreted in Cronje et al. study (1982:20), who affirms those juvenile and criminal offences are not determined by "separate" factors but by the interaction of more than one. These authors' views seem to favour the integrated model approach which marries or combines two or more factors as causes of criminal behaviour.

Writ and Brigg (1965) agreed that delinquency, for instance, can be attributed to any one of many determinants but more so results from a combination of influences from several similar but separate factors. Lekschas, (cited in Cronje *et al.*, 1982:21), adduces that in discussing juvenile offences we are referring to a complexity of factors determining human actions or inactions. Again, there is the existence of a multiplicity of factors that play active roles in the push-pull of people getting involved in criminal activities such as kidnapping, armed robbery, drug trafficking, prostitution, cybercrime and oil theft. This paradigmatic approach to explaining the causes of crime by combining or uniting two or more theoretical factors is

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widely known as the integrated model approach in criminological studies (Agnew, 1992; Elliot, 1985; Huizinga *et al.*, 1988; Brown *et al.*, 1991; Hawkins *et al.*, 1992; Korhauser, 1978, Otu, 2003). It is on this background that this study tends to engage in a critical appraisal of some selected criminological theories and their praxis applications to crime causation in contemporary Nigerian society.

Method

The study adopts a theoretical literature review method. A theoretical literature review in research is a critical examination and synthesis of existing theoretical literature that examines; theoretical frameworks, concepts, and models relevant to a particular research topic (Chukwunoso & Ndubuisi, 2016). This method entails sourcing existing theoretical literature from textbooks, journals, articles and documents to gather relevant information for a given study (Saliu-Yusufand Aliede, 2023). This method enables the researcher to make use of pre-existing data extracted from selected criminological theories that are applied to explain the causes of criminalities in Nigeria. The theoretical method has been proposed by scholars in distinct academic fields and furnished a comprehensive understanding of the theoretical landscape covered by the research topic. The study through the utilization of theoretical review methods explains diverse factors that scholars

identified as causes of crime. The study made use of selected criminological theories to examine different factors why people commit crimes in Nigeria. Biological, Psychological, and Sociological theories were analysed and applied to explain crime in the Nigerian context.

Critical Appraisal of Selected Criminological Theories and Applications to Crime Causation in Contemporary Nigeria:

The six (6) theories and practical applications in Nigeria society that were critically discussed in this study are as follows:

Biological Theory of Crime

Cesare Lombroso is associated with the biological theory of crime. He hypothesized in his study that some humans were naturally carrying with them some biological characteristics that were typical of pre and uncivilized humans. Various traits such as impulsiveness, aggressiveness, and insensitivity to pains, and that these characteristics are antithetical and inimical to contemporary society. These pre-human characteristics are a clear indication of atavism- a reversion or thrown back to an earlier evolutionary stage of man's existence. Accordingly, people possessing these characteristics were born criminals (William, 1988).

He reasoned that biology was a determinant factor for criminality. Hence, the search was

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on the physical and biological attributes that would mark or differentiate criminals from conformists. The biological theory of crime could best be traced to the school, known as human physiognomy, which means the study of facial features and their relation and influence on human conduct. Giambattista delia Porta (1535-1615) maintained that thieves, for instance, possess large lips, and sharp vision. This idea was revisited under the science called “phrenology” which claimed that the existence of certain bumps in the brain were indications of psychological propensities. By the nineteenth century, the sciences of physiognomy and phrenology had introduced specific biogenetic factors into why people engaged in crime.

Cesare Lombroso's (1835-1909) publication of *L'uomo delinquente* (The criminal man) coupled with his theory of the born criminal served as the first and foremost organized view and text on the biological explanation of criminality. Lombroso, who is seen in some quarters as the father of criminology as an academic discipline, stressed that criminals lived a very lower form of life, nearer to their apelike ancestors than non-criminal beings. According to him, criminals are atavistic in nature that is; are thrown back to their primitives alike and they are commonly distinguishable from the non-criminals by various atavistic stigmata-the physical features of creatures at an earlier

stage of human evolution before they become full humans.

Lombroso identified, some physical and biological characteristics, especially from one Italian prisoner named Vilella on whom Cesare Lombroso carried out a post-mortem, his findings were descriptive but fascinating. They revealed the fact that criminals are unusually tall or short, have small heads but large faces, sloping forehead, receding coiffure (hairline), wrinkled forehead, unusually large sinus cavities, bumpy face, large protruding ears, bumps on the head, unusually high cheekbones, cranial bumps, bumps or protuberances in the back of the head, busy eyebrows that make frequent contact, flat nose, generally abnormal teeth and jaw (resembling that of carnivorous), thin, even delicate neck, they have fingers and toes that are either pointy or snubbed, posses extraordinary agility these among other characteristics.

Another biological criminologist, Enrico Ferri, was Lombroso's student, who agreed with Lombroso's biological component for criminal behaviour and also recognised the importance of social, economic and political determinants of crime causation. He rejected the hedonistic doctrine of the classicists and maintained that criminals were pushed to criminality by certain conditions in their lives. Enrico Ferri affirmed that crime was harmful to the fabric of society. Therefore it needs to

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be halted essentially by applying stringent criminal law and through the threat of penalties. Accordingly, Sheldon and Sheldon (1974) also developed the endomorphs- they are lean, with soft and rounded physical build; mesomorphs- they are considered to have strength and muscular development; the ectomorphs- are imbued with little body mass and great surface area. Mesomorphs were considered to be very hung in delinquency. These findings were later strengthened and eulogized by Sheldon Glueck (1896-1980) and Eleanor Glueck (1898-1972).

Toeing the line of the biological study of crime is also the notion that abnormal chromosomal formation, in particular, the XYY configuration can lead to criminal propensity. The XYY is seen as a defective chromosome of a male. In this case, the same two YY chromosomes are received from the father by the child instead of the normal one Y chromosome. Hence, People who possess the XYY are said to be excessively tall, are so aggressive, and frequently violent in nature.

Biological theory can be applied to explain why people engage in crime commission in Nigeria. There is a relationship between biogenic factors and crime in Nigeria. Criminality is biologically determined according to Lombroso and his adherents of biological theorizing. They also emphasized that criminals have facsimile physical attributes and are atavistic in nature.

Using biogenic characteristics to explain the causes of criminality in Nigeria context presupposes that people who engage in political crime /white collar crimes in Nigeria are commonly identified with some pre-human physical features as; protruding bellies, hardened hearts, making fake promises to the masses, liars, chronic womanizing.... this set of criminals are known for money laundering, embezzlement of public funds, tax invasion, misappropriations of fund meant for public project such as roads, schools, hospitals, and others. These characteristics are facsimiles of uncivilized human beings.

Other sets of criminals that are involved in blue-collar crimes as; cybercrime, kidnapping, robbery, banditry, oil theft, and ritual killings are easily distinguishable by keeping dreadlocks similar to that of the insane, wearing earrings like women, wearing under waist and oversized cloths, high intake of hard drugs and chronic womanizing. The bandits, kidnappers, armed robbers, oil bunkering thieves and others who partake in conventional crime are dirty and similar to the ape. Very aggressive, indulge in hard drug intake, uneducated, are bigots, and very insensitive to pain. These explain that Nigerian criminals represent human being who carries with them some characteristics that are suitable for pre-civilized men. That is,

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they are thrown back to their primitive ancestors (who are atavistic in nature).

One of the strong criticisms levelled against bio-physiological criminology theory is that it concretely restricts its research to incarcerated individuals. Again, the theory was criticized for its less rigorous scientific status at the time Lombroso's research was conducted. Bio-criminology has also been berated for failing to acknowledge that individuals have free will.

Lombroso believed that the reversion to primitive beings could be recognized among criminals by the existence of specific physical abnormalities or stigmata that corresponded to those stereotypically attributed to people of African heritage. His idea reflected the colonialist and imperialist policies of 19th-century Europe and infused these prejudices into his theory.

The Psychological Theory of Crime

At the heart of the psychological theory, therefore, is the assumption that crime is the result of the personality crisis an individual experiences. This is a reflection of the pattern of socialization processes the individual passed through. Psychological theory locates the causes of criminal tendencies in the individual criminals, albeit, "covertly", not like the outward manifestations of the biochemical theories. The idea of this theory is that deviant's sickness and abnormal behaviour lie innately

in the inner mind of an individual, rather than in the outward human body (Haralambos and Holborn 1991; 583-85).

Psychogenic theory of crime, as in some quarters referred to it emanates from the shift from the emphasis on the presumed outward physical manifestations to the hidden, psyche traits of deviant behaviour. As Sykes (1978:241-42) notes, there was a shift of interest from defective intelligence, to a more conscious conflict within individual. Crime was observed as a product of the bursting forth of "id" impulses, and the criminal is simply dramatizing what most enlightened and civilized men and women had learned to restrain (see also Tarde 1890).

Abrahamson (1945) explains that criminality and delinquent behaviour are the outcomes of mental disconnection or impairment signs of serious psychosis in humans. The thrust of the psychological theory is to carefully study and understand the defective behavioural result of a child, who lacks proper socialization to carefully moderate his or her egoistic forces before becoming a full adult. Such personality traits as impulsivity, aggressiveness, psychoses, sadism, lack of compassion, emotional immaturity, insensitivity to others and hyperactivity have been most focused on among psychologists.

Sigmund Freud (1856- 1939), succinctly relates and equates crime and

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delinquency to a conscience which is somehow overbearing and plays a part in arousing feelings of guilt or being too weak to control an individual's natural impulses. Three components of personality were identified by Freud as the id, ego and super-ego. He described the **id**- as the raw and untamed biological and psychological "drives" that underlie all human behaviours including libido- the urge for sex. In his analysis, the "id" represents the unconscious, and is always in need of immediate self-gratification. The "**super-ego**" is the image of the conscience, moral and ethical values of an individual which is an internalized parental standard and reflects the value of the society, while the "**ego**" is the conscience component that mediates between the push-pull of the "id" and "super-ego". So, according to Freud, a force of balance is supposedly maintained in all individuals, and at all times of temptations. When the "id" overshadows the "super-ego", or when the "ego" is weak or fails to perform its' arbitrate role, criminality will result.

John Bowlby (1946 cf. Haralambos and Holborn 1991:583-85) in his renowned work titled "Forty-four Juvenile Thieves," discussed criminality and deviant behaviour from the angle of socialization. He argued that children need emotional security, particularly during their first seven years of life. This only can adequately be provided by the child's natural mother with a close, intimate and

loving relationship. When a child is deprived of this, particularly during the early years, a psychopathic personality could develop. The child tends to act impulsively with little regard for the consequences. Bowlby, then, claimed that delinquents who were chronic recidivists (constant breakers of law with little regard for the consequence) had suffered maternal deprivation during their early years.

We can use the psychological theory of crime to analyze why people took to crime in Nigeria. A careful observation of some criminals in Nigeria shows that they suffer from internal disorder and the reasons for their participation in crime can be located within the individual. Also, some individual who engage in criminality in Nigeria claim to lack parental care, especially during their early childhood, and they represent those who were not properly socialized with the norms and values of society. In Nigeria oftentimes time you hear confessions in the form of criminal charges defences from criminals as; I don't know what came over me- meaning they were under some sort of influence and can't control what they were doing. Again, in this society some offenders have confessed to a lack of parental care at an early age hence, they result to committing crimes to carter for themselves. Haralambos and Holborn (1991: 584) aptly outlined the critical criticisms of psychogenic theory, especially by sociologists and criminologists. Firstly, the theory was berated

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for its negligence of social and cultural factors as they account for criminality and deviance. Also, human are not tied to their childhood experience. Most times, youngsters who were socialized in the midst of hardship have higher success records as adults.

Strain Theory of Crime

The theory of strain serves as a representation of the sociological position to account for crime. The major crux of the theoretical postulate of strain averts that stress and frustration (strain) hence the name, are mainly caused by failed aspirations of individuals, therefore, they increase the propensity of norm violation. Strain theory maintains that norms are not obeyed or that, people indulge in crimes as a means of easing away the strains and stress that are caused by denial, frustration and failure which can lead to aggressive conduct. Lack of access to the attainment of set goals makes it mandatory to seek alternative routes for the achievement of societal goals.

Brown et al. (1991:298), carefully observed that strain is fused with distorted aims and aspirations, people's unrealized desires for the attainment of set goals. Most strain theorists reasoned that the structure of modern society, and in particular, American society, creates the greatest pressure on the lower-class group. Variants of strain theory include; Anomie, Goals-means, Sub-cultural, Differential opportunity and Ecological theories of crime.

The crux of strain theorists like other sociological-criminological theories is that they tried to understand the economic situation of the people in the society and how this can result in criminal behaviour.

Strain theory can be applied to explain the causes or the reason why people engage in crime in Nigerian society. Using the Niger Delta Region as a case study, the region is blessed with crude oil that produces the wealth of Nigeria and the people of this region especially the youths hope to live a better life if they are supported by the government from the huge sum of money that is derived from the natural resources of the region. The activities of oil exploration by multinational companies have also made the region very unattractive for agricultural activities. Hence, parents who are majorly farmers cannot send their children to school. This blocked the opportunities to set goals leading to frustration and failure on the path of the youth. Therefore this scenario makes the youth of the region engage in the crime of oil bunkering/oil theft, kidnapping, robbery, cybercrime and other crimes to seek solace and to ease their frustration.

Robert Merton: Means-End Theory (1938).

Robert Merton (1938), was a loyal supporter of Durkheim's postulates, he modified and rebranded the anomie theory that Clinard (1964:10), romantically eulogised. Merton begins his analysis with the understanding that

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every society has a cultural system, and this embodies the society-approved values and goals, and the acceptable standard of norms or institutionalized means created by the society for the achievement of these goals. But, unfortunately, the agreed societal goals and means do not allow all the members to pursue only success in legitimate ways. The institutionalized means for achieving success are of course, not openly and equally available to all the members of the same society. Both the goals and means exert pressure on some segments of the society in non-conforming behaviour as they struggle to achieve these success goals and values. In Merton's view, this happens when the goal of success is emphasized more than the acceptable ways of achieving success.

As Robert Merton (1938) rightly put it “society creates its own unique brand of crimes and criminals by establishing its goals, standards and moral values without making provision for appropriate legal opportunities for achieving the set goals”. He notes that in the absence of legitimate or institutionalized means people tend to be innovative and engage in illegal activities such as; kidnapping, armed robbery, oil theft, cybercrime and other criminal activities to achieve success goals. Merton notes that it is not all persons who lack the legal means to achieve societal goals legally that will follow such alternative routes to success in society.

It is apparent that in all known societies, members of the lower class echelon have fewer opportunities for quality education and important interpersonal networks that can improve their opportunities and access to better lives. These access to opportunities mould individuals to compete in their struggle to achieve success goals, wealth, and social prestige. Hence, people especially the lower class experience difficulties, and strain in their aspirations to achieve this success legitimately. On this account, Merton argues that it is these blocked opportunities that explain the reasons for the high number of lower-class members engaging in criminal and delinquent acts. Therefore, an inequitable social structure evaluating success similarly at all social or societal levels produces the lower class strain and ultimately leads to crime and delinquency (see Merton, 1938).

Merton identified five possible ways people respond to structural stress since not all people are deviant. This can be referred to as Merton's "plus-minus paradigm".

CONFORMITY: This set of people accept culturally defined goals and adhere to the legal means to achieving them, despite their success or failure.

INNOVATION: This represents the most common form of adaptation to structural stress. It clearly explains a scenario where the illegal routes to success are adopted to achieve the

commonly held goals by society members.

RITUALISTS: This is the opposite of innovation, and it consists of people who abide by the rules (means) but lack commitments to the agreed goals. These categories include priests, civil servants and teachers.

RETREATISTS: These groups represent the social dropouts. It portrayed those who abandoned both the cultural goals as well as the legal means to success. Very good examples are; drug addicts, homeless and truants. The adaptors will simply withdraw from their society into their own shells (Thio, 1998: 19). In fact these sets of people live in their own world.

REBELLION: They are those who reject the goals and means of society and substitute them with new sets of values and norms for the discarded ones. Examples of this category include political revolutionaries and religious extremists.

Means-end theory can be used to explain the causes of criminality in Nigeria. This is because the culture of this society has socialized its members to believe that there are prescribed standards and goals and corresponding legitimate means of achieving them. But the reality in Nigeria is that the

legitimate means of achieving the set goals by society are not equally or overly available to the poor masses. In lieu of this people tend to be innovative, that is using illegal means to achieve success goals. Hence, Nigerians especially the youths are involved in committing all sorts of crimes. The Nigerian culture had made its citizens for example have the understanding that when you graduate from high institutions one can secure a good job to survive and help family members, but the means of going to high school to acquire a degree is not overtly available to the lower class. This explains why most youths are actively engaging in criminal activities to prepare the ground for a better future. Most Nigerian students today are waxing stronger in cybercrime as a means of reaching success. As the Nigeria EFCC chairman affirmed in December (2023); “seven out of ten Nigerian students are involved in cybercrimes or, are cybercriminals”. Also, in Nigeria graduating from high school is no guarantee for a white-collar job. Hence, many Nigerians, especially the youth survive through crime, as the culture of their society has turned its citizens into criminals. This justifies Merton's aphorism that every society helps to create its own brand/kind of crimes and criminals. In Nigeria today, the way you make your wealth is no longer important, money is reverend in families, and churches without checking the source. This helps to explain the upsurge of

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people's activeness in criminalities in the country.

Merton's theory has been **criticised** for its many inconsistencies and Broidy (2001:9) states that its scope is limited because it focuses exclusively on lower-class boys in an urban environment. Braithwaite (1981) and Title and Meier (1990), have also criticized the theory.

Differential Opportunity Theory

The theory of differential opportunity by Cloward and Ohlin (1960) is also a version of Merton and Cohen's theories. Towing the basic premise of strain theory, the authors explain that it is not always automatic for lower-class people confronted with the lack of opportunity to engage in criminality or deviance. People's engagement in deviant acts depends on the degree of their confrontation or access to the illegitimate opportunity structure. Although most lower-class people lack access to legitimate and conforming activities, they do not have the same opportunity for participation in illegitimate and deviant activities. In other words, there is differential illegitimate opportunity. For example, in a particular area, there may be a surviving senior criminal subculture that provides conducive conditions for youngsters; this may not be available in other areas. In the first area, adolescents can have ample chances to learn a successful criminal career than in the second environment. Critical to the

differential opportunity theory is that criminal behaviour and delinquent activities in which one becomes immersed are a direct function of the delinquent opportunities available. In other words, what differential opportunity theory is saying is that to become a criminal and delinquent, there must be an organized structure which provides the illegitimate opportunity structures that could facilitate the development of criminal and delinquent adaptations to anomic conditions.

By this, Cloward and Ohlin's theory affirmed that being committed to criminality is not an easy profession and is also beset with all the uncertainties and constraints associated with legitimate activity. An illegitimate opportunity structure like the legitimate one presupposes social organizations or integration in order to offer illegal opportunities. A person seeking innovative solutions to his strained circumstances must equally learn the necessary values and skills to take full advantage of the opportunity such structure offers within the society. Those who lack these proper skills and potential, they argued, will again confront failure in their efforts to become criminals, say, for example, cybercrime, armed robbers, and oil theft.

Cloward and Ohlin propose that three types of delinquent subcultures emerge. **The criminal subculture** offers illegitimate opportunities to reach success goals. There is an organised adult criminal subculture which

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provides an enabling learning environment for the young ones-impacting in them the necessary skills and values. Criminal subculture is mainly concerned with utilitarian crime. Criminal adults are presented as role models. **The conflict subculture** offers illegitimate opportunities only to those youngsters who can meet certain stringent requirements such as great fighting skills and fearless risk-taking. There is little organised adult crime to provide apprenticeship for the young up-coming criminals. **The retreatist subculture** focuses on the use of drugs as members have failed to achieve status and success in the criminal or conflict subcultures. They are simply double failures in terms of the legitimate and illegitimate opportunity structures.

In Nigeria, this theory can be used to explain why different crime thrives, and why they are identified with different regions of the country. The theory explains that for one to become a criminal there must be the existence of an organized structure that will help provide illegal opportunities that could necessarily facilitate the development of criminal adaptation to anomic situation.

For example, the Southwest of Nigeria is famous for cybercrime, herder-farmer conflict, extrajudicial killings, armed robbery, abduction, domestic crime, ritual killings and others. The South-East is known for; Banditry, ritual killings, commercial crime,

secessionist agitation, kidnapping, herders-farmers dispute, and unknown gunmen attack. Also, the North-East region serves as a soft spot for Boko Haram Insurgency. While the South-South region is well known for militancy, oil bunkery, kidnapping, and environmental agitations. And the northern region is popular with the crime of banditry, illegal mining and assassinations. The point is that youth in the South-South can easily learn and master the crime of oil theft than for instance the North-West youths. This is because the South-South region is endowed with natural resources, and there exist senior mentors that can help young ones facilitate the learning of the crime of crude theft than in the North-West that does not have the resources and models for oil theft. The theory was **criticized** for its operational deficiency of concepts used. Reid (1982 ct. Iwarimie-Jaja 1999a:74), opined that it was weak in defining concepts such as "double failures", "perception of opportunity", denial of legitimacy", differential opportunity" and "elimination of guilt".

Differential Association Theory

Edwin Sutherland's [1949] differential association theory is described as the first truly sociological criminology effort to explain crime (Brown et al., 1991:340). This theory- like its parent one- imitation is very important in understanding criminalities such as; kidnapping, cybercrime, and armed

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robbery in today's Nigeria. Sutherland's starting point was a conflict orientation to society. He conceived of society as made up of different social groups and classes who believed in and adhered to very different beliefs about what was right and wrong. He therefore argued that people were exposed to a variety of behavioural patterns of both criminal and non-criminal.

Being greatly influenced by Gabriel Tarde's (1843-1904) "law of imitation" (1890 and interpreted by Parsons, 1903), and other theories such as symbolic interactionism, culture transmission, and culture conflicts; Sutherland argues that persons socialised in the socially disorganised neighbourhood are likely to have an association that will increase criminal adaptations. In contrast, those individuals from socially organised neighbourhoods are more likely to experience non-criminal association. Aligning with the Chicago School of thought, he notes that crime is socially distributed, and is indeed a learned behaviour in a social environment. According to (William & Mcshane, 1994:70), Sutherland affirmed that all behaviour (criminal and noncriminal) is learned, in the same way. The major difference between conforming and criminal behaviour is what is learned, rather than how. His concern, therefore, was to study and understand the learning processes.

While researching the "Professional Thief" (1973) for example, he identified the tutelage necessary for both admittance and practice of the trade. In his best-known work: "The White Collar Crime" (1949), he demanded that crime should be defined to include offences of persons in the upper socio-economic class. This according to him will explain the diverse range of factors such as age, gender, race, and socio-economic status, associated with crime, however, not casually. So dear to sociologists and criminologists as found in his research works are the nine principles of the theory he propounded in 1947, and are always appearing in all his edited criminological texts. The principles identify the social process by which individual comes to engage and perpetuate criminal behaviour (see Sutherland and Cressey, 1940:75). The principles of the theory ruled out hereditary, human nature, meta-physical or myth, and innovation as some of the causes of illegal behaviour. People are not born with criminogenic tendencies, but rather develop criminaloid, he had argued. The principles as contained in most of the texts are summarised below:

- 1) Criminal behaviour is learned and not inherited.
- 2) Criminal behaviour is learned in interaction with other persons in a process of communication.

- 3) That the principal part of the learning of criminal behaviour occurs within intimate personal groups (negatively meaning that impersonal agencies of communication such as movies, newspapers, radio, and the internet play a relatively unimportant part in the genesis of learning criminal behaviour).
 - 4) The learning includes (i) Understanding the techniques of committing the crime, which sometimes is very complicated, and at other times very simple. (ii) the specific direction of the motive and drives rationalization and attitudes for crime commission.
 - 5) People learn the specific direction of the motives from the definitions of the legal code as favourable or unfavourable. In some communities, individuals interact with persons who always define the content of the legal codes as a rule to be observed or by individuals whose definitions are favourable to the violation of the content of the legal codes.
 - 6) An individual can learn criminal habits because of the abundance of definitions favourable to the breaking of the law over definitions not favourable to law-breaking. When individuals become criminals, they do so because of interaction with criminal patterns and also because of disconnection from anti-criminal patterns.
 - 7) Associating differentially with people may vary in terms of frequency, duration, priority and intensity. Priority is seen in this regard to be very essential in the view that the lawful behaviour developed in early childhood may persist throughout life while delinquent behaviour developed in the same vein may persist over time.
 - 8) The ways of learning the act of committing crime by association with criminal and anti-criminal patterns involve all the processes that are involved in any other social learning.
 - 9) While criminal behaviour is an expression of general needs and values, these general needs and values do not explain criminality because non-criminal behaviour is also an expression of the same needs and values. Thieves generally steal to make money and likewise, honest labourers work hard in order to secure money. (Sutherland & Cressey, 1974:75-76)
- Specifically, Sutherland argued that people will engage in criminal behaviour only when they have acquired sentiments in favour of law violation that outstrips conformity.
- The assumptions of Differential Association theory make it one of the best fits to explain criminalities in contemporary Nigeria. Some of the critical assumptions of the theory are: That criminality is learned just like any other normal behaviour, and people

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who are socialized in a criminal environment are more likely to learn and perpetuate crime than those raised in a non-criminal neighbourhood. Also, people feel free to be criminals due to an excess of definitions that are favourable to norm violation over definitions not favourable to law-breaking.

Corruption, oppression, and injustice loom large on the path of Nigerian leaders hence, every average Nigerian Citizen is faced with difficulties to survive as this encourages criminalities in the nation's environment. In this society, many individuals are engaged in criminal activities in a way. Therefore, the Nigerian environs serve as a platform where crime can be easily learned. Again, a sizeable population of the country sees crime as a norm, this reflects the fact that as people interact in the Nigerian space, they are always in contact with people who give favourable definitions to crime than those who see crime as evil. More so, in their social interactions, people with different criminal values are always in close contact and they exchange different techniques on how to commit more crimes. The nature of Nigerian prisons where both convicted and awaiting trial persons are warehoused in the same space also encourages criminalities. And these scenarios explain why more people in Nigeria, are engaged in criminal activities.

Conclusion

This study on critical appraisal of selected criminological theories and applications to crime causation in Nigeria has demonstrated that the causes of crime can be explained theoretically with a single factor or by marrying two or more factors (integrated approach) in accounting for why people engage in criminalities. This study hoped that criminologists would be able to understand and help solve the problem of crime through the use of criminological theories to understand and explain reasons for criminalities in society, and Nigeria in particular. **Theories** and **practice** form what we know today as "academic criminology". No sound criminological theories No academic criminology.

Recommendations

Relevant authorities in the fight against crime such as law enforcement agents, policymakers, and leaders should be encouraged to have in-depth knowledge of theories in criminology to learn the reasons that animate different individuals to engage in criminalities. This will assist in directing their actions and policies toward crime control and reduction in contemporary society.

Using criminological theories to explain crime in practical terms in Nigeria higher institutions of academic learning should be made mandatory, as this will help in exposing the various factors that encourage criminalities in Nigerian society. That is,

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crime theories should be used to explain practical crimes in the academic cycle.

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